

Thiazolidones. Part VI

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Syntheses of 3-benzyl-2-arylimino- and 5-alkyl/aryl-2-benzylimino-4-thiazolidones have been effected.

When an unsymmetrically substituted thiourea is condensed with monochloroacetic acid, there is a possibility of obtaining isomeric 4-thiazolidones.

In many cases only one of the two isomers is formed¹. Davis and Dains² have condensed *N*-phenyl-*N'*-alkyl benzylthiourea with ethyl chloroacetate and found the condensation products to be 3-alkyl/benzyl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidone. In this communication *N'*-aryl-*N''*-(substituted)benzylthioureas have been condensed with monochloroacetic acid in presence of sodium acetate in absolute ethanol. The constitution of the condensation product was settled as follows :

(i) By analogy with the work of Davis and Dains² these compounds were assumed to be 3-benzyl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidones.

(ii) The condensation product of *N'*-phenyl-*N''*-benzylthiourea with monochloroacetic acid was hydrolysed when a product was obtained which was identical (m.p., mixed m.p.) with 3-benzyl-2,4-thiazolidione, prepared from *sym*-dibenzylthiourea and monochloroacetic acid by the method of Bhargava *et al*³. 2,4-Thiazolidione was benzylated, following the method of Bradsher *et al*⁴.

5-Alkyl/aryl-2-benzylimino-4-thiazolidones have been prepared by the condensation of benzylthioureas with α -halo-fatty acids and α -halo-arylacetic acids respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Substituted benzylthioureas were prepared as described by Trivedi *et al*⁵. α -Halo-arylacetic acids were prepared as described by Raval and Trivedi⁶.

1. Davis *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem.*, 1921, **43**, 614.
2. *Ibid.*, 1935, **37**, 2627.
3. *This Journal*, 1955, **32**, 463.
4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 6189.
5. *This Journal*, 1956, **33**, 423; 1958, **35**, 637.
6. *Ibid.*, 1959, **36**, 733.

Condensation of *N'*-benzyl-*N''*-phenylthioureas with monochloroacetic acid to obtain 3-benzyl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidones, of benzylthiourea with α -halo-aliphatic acid and α -halo-arylacetic acid to get 5-alkyl-2-benzylimino-4-thiazolidones and 5-aryl-2-benzylimino-4-thiazolidones respectively was carried out as described by Raval and Trivedi⁶.

Hydrolysis of 3-Benzyl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone.—A mixture of thiazolidone (4.9 g.), absolute ethanol (20 ml) and HCl (25ml, dil.) was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hours. The mixture was poured on a large volume of water and filtered. The solid was repeatedly washed with water to remove the acid completely. The compound was dried and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 61°.

The presence of aniline hydrochloride in the filtrate was confirmed by the preparation of its azo compound with β -naphthol. The compounds are described in Tables I and II.

TABLE I
3-(Subst.)-benzyl-2-(subst.)-phenylimino-4-thiazolidones

Compounds. R.	M.P.	Formula. R'=H.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.
H	68°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	11.5	11.3
<i>o</i> -Cl	79°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₂ ClS	10.3	10.1
<i>m</i> -Cl	110°	"	9.9	10.1
<i>p</i> -Cl	59°	"	10.2	10.1
<i>o</i> -Me	75°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S	10.9	10.8
<i>p</i> -Me	60°	"	10.7	10.8
<i>p</i> -Br	92°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ON ₂ BrS	9.0	8.9
<i>o</i> -OMe	75°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.4	10.3
<i>p</i> -OMe	80°	"	10.5	10.3
R'=o-Cl.				
H	93°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ ClS	10.3	10.1
<i>o</i> -Cl	78°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	9.0	9.1
<i>m</i> -Cl	114°	"	9.3	9.1
<i>p</i> -Cl	98°	"	9.2	9.1
<i>o</i> -Me	106°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ON ₂ ClS	9.9	9.7
<i>m</i> -Me	107°	"	9.8	9.7
<i>p</i> -Me	72°	"	9.6	9.7
<i>p</i> -Br	94°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ON ₂ ClBrS	8.3	8.1
<i>o</i> -OMe	110°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	9.3	9.2
<i>p</i> -OMe	114°	"	9.4	9.2
R'=p-Cl.				
H	84°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ ClS	10.3	10.1
<i>o</i> -Cl	95°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	9.2	9.1
<i>m</i> -Cl	80°	"	9.0	9.1
<i>p</i> -Cl	94°	"	9.3	9.1
<i>o</i> -Me	58°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ON ₂ ClS	9.8	9.7
<i>m</i> -Me	80°	"	9.5	9.7
<i>p</i> -Me	100°	"	9.6	9.7
<i>p</i> -Br	104°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ON ₂ ClBrS	8.3	8.1
<i>o</i> -OMe	92°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	9.4	9.2
<i>p</i> -OMe	102°	"	9.3	9.2

TABLE II

5-Alkyl/aryl-2-benzylimino-4-thiazolidones.

X.	M.P.	Formula.	%S u l p h u r.	
			Found.	Reqd.
		R = Me.		
H	141°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ ON ₂ S	14.6	14.5
<i>o</i> -Cl	165°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON ₂ ClS	12.5	12.8
<i>p</i> -Cl	170°	"	12.7	"
<i>m</i> -Me	125°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	13.7	13.7
<i>p</i> -Me	154°	"	13.6	"
3,4-DiMe	128°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S	12.7	12.9
2,4-DiMe	160°	"	12.9	"
2,5-DiMe	130°	"	12.8	"
<i>p</i> -Br	167°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON ₂ BrS	10.9	10.7
		R = Et.		
H	139°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	13.9	13.7
<i>o</i> -Cl	112°	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON ₂ ClS	11.8	11.9
<i>p</i> -Cl	153°	"	12.0	"
<i>m</i> -Me	127°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S	13.0	12.9
<i>p</i> -Me	134°	"	12.8	"
3,4-DiMe	140°	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ ON ₂ S	12.0	12.2
2,4-DiMe	110°	"	12.4	"
2,5-DiMe	130°	"	12.1	"
<i>p</i> -Br	144°	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON ₂ BrS	10.4	10.2
		R = Bu ⁿ .		
H	128°	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ ON ₂ S	12.1	12.2
<i>o</i> -Cl	131°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ ON ₂ ClS	10.6	10.3
<i>p</i> -Cl	156°	"	11.0	"
<i>m</i> -Me	125°	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ ON ₂ S	11.5	11.6
<i>p</i> -Me	150°	"	11.8	"
3,4-DiMe	132°	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ ON ₂ S	10.9	11.0
2,4-DiMe	139°	"	11.2	"
2,5-DiMe	73°	"	11.1	"
<i>p</i> -Br	134°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ ON ₂ BrS	9.2	9.4
		R = Ph.		
H	173°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	11.2	11.3
<i>o</i> -Cl	140°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ ClS	10.0	10.1
<i>p</i> -Cl	202°	"	10.2	"
<i>m</i> -Me	150°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S	10.9	10.8
<i>p</i> -Me	150°	"	10.7	"
<i>p</i> -OMe	180°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.2	10.3
3,4-DiMe	160°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ON ₂ S	10.1	10.3
2,4-DiMe	160°	"	10.4	"
2,5-DiMe	182°	"	10.2	"
<i>o</i> -Br	151°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ BrS	8.8	8.9
<i>m</i> -Br	123°	"	8.7	"
<i>p</i> -Br	205°	"	9.0	"

TABLE II (contd.)

X.	M.P.	Formula. R=o-Cl.Ph.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.
H	80°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ ClS	10.0	10.1
o-Cl	88°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	9.0	9.1
p-Cl	90°	"	9.2	"
m-Me	141°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ON ₂ ClS	9.8	9.7
p-Me	90°	"	9.6	"
m-Br	126°	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ ON ₂ ClBrS	8.2	8.1

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